

ORIGIN AND CELEBRATION OF KINDERGARTEN DAY IN URUGUAY

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Uruguay is a South American country located in the eastern part of the southern cone. Its territory is small compared to its neighbors Brazil and Argentina. It has an approximate population of 3.3 million inhabitants and its main production is agricultural - livestock. The country has a free public education system that covers up to the tertiary level and a high literacy rate.

Every March 10, almost at the beginning of the school year, “Kindergarten Day” is celebrated in Uruguayan's initial education institutions. This date remembers the founding of the first Kindergarten in the country and of formal and public education in Latin America in 1892, at the request of the Catalan-Uruguayan teacher Enriqueta Compte y Riqué.

This article aims to briefly review the process that gave rise to the date of celebration and also highlight the contributions of this educator who was a pioneer in pedagogical research and preschool teaching throughout the continent.

1 The origin of the celebration

The initiative to promote this celebration comes from members of the World Organization for Preschool Education in Uruguay (OMEP-Uruguay: The World Organization for Preschool Education in Uruguay was founded in 1957. <https://www.omep.org.uy/>) who presented the proposal in the plenary session of the III Education Congress (The holding of education congresses is stipulated in Education Law No. 18437 of 2008) held in 2017. It should be noted that this congress was named “Enriqueta Compte y Riqué” in recognition of her enormous contribution to education, the result of her innovative outlook and her committed actions. This is how the request to the education authorities to formally specify this initiative arises from the plenary session of the congress.

On March 10, 2018, “Kindergarten Day” begins to be celebrated throughout the country. The CODICEN (Consejo Directivo Central de la Administración nacional de Educación Pública <https://www.anep.edu.uy/codicen>) resolution that authorizes it recognizes the validity of the founding principles of Enriqueta Compte y Riqué and establishes that for its commemoration, the organization and coordination of activities that contribute to prioritizing early childhood education and care in compliance with children's rights be promoted in ANEP (Administración Nacional de Educación Pública. <https://www.anep.edu.uy/>) educational centers. (National Administration of Public Education, 2018, p. 3).

In accordance with this initiative, OMEP-Uruguay is also carrying out the proposal for a project called: “Enriqueta Compte y Riqué Kindergarten Constellation.” Considering that one of the tasks of the OMEP is the dissemination of actions and proposals that promote the rights of early childhood and quality education and, taking into account that these tasks coincide with the objectives of the General Directorate of Early Childhood and Primary Education (Dirección General de Educación Inicial y Primaria – DGEIP <https://www.dgeip.edu.uy/documentos/2023/portal/index.html>), it is intended to promote, through this joint project, the nomination of Kindergartens with the name Enriqueta Compte y Riqué in the 19 departments of the country, forming a network or constellation of Institutions that have the same name (OMEP, s/f, a).

The fundamental objective of this project is to revalue the pedagogical ideas developed in Uruguay by this significant personality of national pedagogy. In that same direction, the project proposes to promote

theoretical reflection and the enrichment of practices in Kindergartens that make up the “Enriqueta Compte and Riqué Kindergarten Constellation”, through study, exchange of proposals and experiences between teams of teachers, other technicians and professionals, children and families.

In 2019, the Council of Initial and Primary Education (Consejo de Educación Inicial y Primaria; current DGEIP), considers the project presented by OMEP – Uruguay as of “very high interest for the educational community” and resolves to authorize its implementation (OMEP, s/f,b) . Thus, to the date of celebration of “Kindergarten Day” an action that promotes networking, emphasizing teacher training, teamwork and the exchange of experiences.

The text of the project substantiates the relevance of strengthening the teaching task to enrich the experiences and learning of children while disseminating the pedagogical ideas of Enriqueta Compte and Riqué, her life and work. By enhancing the knowledge of teaching groups and generating possibilities for exchange, the specific pedagogical lines of early childhood education are prioritized, taking into account the rich national history; at the same time, innovations are promoted from the classrooms in dialogue with the founding ideas of our Initial Education.

2 Profile of a precursor

Enriqueta Compte y Riqué was born in Barcelona in 1866 but emigrated to Uruguay with her family while she was still a child. In Uruguay she studied teaching, graduating at 19 years of age. It was in this country where, in addition to creating the first kindergarten, she developed all her work and her absolutely innovative thinking for the time.

In 1887 she was appointed deputy director of the Normal Institute for Ladies with the possibility of impacting the training of future teachers. She later traveled to Europe on an official mission, sent by the government to specialize in preschool education. She was entrusted with the task of internalizing the teachings of Friedrich Fröbel, and the contributions of the New School directly, which is why she toured Belgium, Germany, Holland, France and Switzerland.

Ivaldi (2009), in researching her legacy, maintains that Enriqueta found it difficult to capture the richness of her practice in formal publications. That is why most of her ideas are contained in official documents and in compilations of her conferences. From there we can extract her valuable contributions and glimpse her intellectual restlessness characterized by constant questioning and well-founded criticism that rejects the mere acceptance of theoretical models without passing them through the sieve of reflection. Enriqueta Compte y Riqué was also a woman committed to the circumstances of her historical time. That is why she actively participated in causes such as the fight against tuberculosis, the prevention of alcoholism, the female vote, the organization of teachers in favor of their training and defense of their rights, the protection of orphans and the accompaniment of prisoners to promote their reintegration into the community. Thus, she demonstrated not only his social sensitivity but also a position that considers and analyzes the relationships between education and politics.

Some of her most relevant points can be highlighted from her vast work.

- She was a follower of the ideas of José Pedro Varela (José Pedro Varela (1845- Montevideo- 1879) writer, journalist and politician recognized as the reformer of Uruguayan public education) that education should begin at an early age within the framework of the principles of secularism, free and compulsory education. With respect to the levels of concreteness of these principles, education in the Kindergartens was free from its beginning. She managed to advance in her process towards secularism

marked by the political rhythm of the time and although the obligation did not come to fruition, Enriqueta Compte y Riqué's constant concern to promote the creation of new Kindergartens is evident.

- From the experience of her travels, she manages to incorporate pedagogical methods inspired by the New School with the purpose of enhancing all the capabilities of the human being from its earliest age.
- Her pedagogical ideas are based on the recognition and respect for the uniqueness of each boy or girl, taking into account their needs, possibilities and interests. In the speech given in 1945 on the occasion of her retirement, she gives an account of her interest in singularity:

As soon as I began school functions, I told my co-workers that the child had to be cared for and studied individually, taking note of all the manifestations that were characteristic of him in the physical, intellectual and moral order. (General Directorate of Initial and Primary Education, 1946).

- She was a promoter of the introduction of innovative work methodologies such as the production of school biographies. In them, teachers made written records regarding the development and characteristics of each child with the aim of knowing the real child and considering their uniqueness. She also developed the practice of incident records in which life events that occurred during a lesson or outside of it were narrated. She also incorporated the use of photographic recording to capture classroom scenes, an absolutely innovative practice for the time.
- She was a defender of the profession and proposals related to teacher training. She also defends, throughout her professional career, the teacher's freedom in the application of school programs.

She died on October 18, 1949 in Montevideo, Uruguay.

3 Celebrating Enriqueta today

To date, “Kindergarten Day” is celebrated in the country's institutions with renewed energy every year. That day, together with families and educational communities in the centers, the organization of activities that contribute to prioritizing initial education in line with the ideas of Enriqueta Compte y Riqué and the children's rights are promoted.

Currently, continuity is also being given to the nomination processes that were already being carried out in various departments of the country within the framework of the “Enriqueta Compte y Riqué Kindergarten Constellation” project.

Enriqueta Compte and Riqué. Photo in the archives of the José Pedro Varela Pedagogical Museum.

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